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Toward Reproducible Benchmarking of PGAS and MPI Communication Schemes

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Abstract—With the forthcoming age of exascale computing, the efficient support of different programming models has become a crucial performance factor for high-performance computing systems. When adopting novel programming paradigms, the performance assessment through reproducible and comparable benchmarks plays an essential role in both the effective use of the heterogeneous system hardware and the application performance tuning. Alternatives to MPI such as the partitioned global address space (PGAS) model have become increasingly popular. One such PGAS API is the Global Address Space Programming Interface (GASPI). This paper introduces the GASPI Benchmark Suite (GBS), which combines a comprehensive set of microbenchmarks with application kernels. The microbenchmarks target common GASPI communication patterns, including one-sided, collective, passive, and global atomics, while the application kernels stress communication schemes commonly found in real HPC applications. The effectiveness of GBS is demonstrated by evaluating the GASPI communication performance for the networking communication standard InfiniBand.

Index Terms—PGAS, Reproducible Benchmarking, GASPI

I. INTRODUCTION

For many years, the *Message Passing Interface* (MPI) has been considered the de-facto standard in the high-performance computing (HPC) community when it comes to developing parallel applications. One alternative to MPI is the *Global Address Space Programming Interface* (GASPI) [1]–[3], which provides researchers and scientific application developers with one-sided RDMA-driven communication based on the *Partitioned Global Address Space* (PGAS) [4] parallel programming model. When adopting novel programming interfaces such as GASPI, the performance assessment through standardized and comparable benchmarks plays an essential role in both the effective use of the heterogeneous system hardware and the application performance tuning. Comprehensive benchmark suites can be used to evaluate the potential performance for various communication patterns and different HPC compute environments.

In this work, our contributions are twofold. First, we consider the requirements for designing reproducible benchmarks for evaluating and comparing parallel programming models, using GASPI as an example. For this purpose, we first analyze existing microbenchmarks. Second, we introduce the *GASPI Benchmark Suite* (GBS), which provides a collection of microbenchmarks and application kernels for the GASPI API. Its design relies on a comprehensive approach, which provides a

basis for the development of a standardized and reproducible PGAS and MPI benchmark methodology. GBS offers a useful mean of measuring performance and assessing the effects of new features as well as implementation strategies.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In the following, we first describe the PGAS model and one of its implementations called GASPI. We conclude this section by discussing relevant related work.

A. Partitioned Global Address Space (PGAS)

The *Partitioned Global Address Space* (PGAS) model is an alternative parallel programming paradigm to MPI designed to simplify the development of high-performance parallel applications. In PGAS, memory is logically divided into global address spaces, with each partition typically associated with a specific processing unit or node in a parallel system. This model provides a global view of memory, allowing all processing units to access data across the entire system, akin to a single shared address space. Key features of the PGAS model include local memory for each processing unit, enabling efficient data access, explicit data placement for fine-grained control over data locality, and one-sided communication, which permits direct data reads and writes in remote processes without explicit synchronization. PGAS models facilitate load balancing and data distribution, ensuring work is evenly distributed among processing units for optimal parallel performance. The concept is implemented in various ways as extensions to existing programming languages such as Unified Parallel C (UPC) and Co-Array Fortran (CAF) or as software libraries like OpenSHMEM and GASPI. However, PGAS models have no strict definition.

B. Global Address Space Programming Interface (GASPI)

The *Global Address Space Programming Interface* (GASPI) [1]–[3] is a parallel programming model and PGAS-API designed to simplify the programming task and at the same time facilitate data-locality, thread-based programming and asynchronous communication. GASPI is mostly comparable to OpenSHMEM as it incorporates explicit remote read or write routines and does not support true global address space access like UPC. GASPI’s goal is to initiate a paradigm shift from bulk-synchronous two-sided message exchange towards an asynchronous data-flow and execution

Fig. 1: Segmented partitioned global address space in GASPI.

model while supporting the segmentation of the memory in multiple parts, as shown in Figure 1. These memory segments can be defined differently on every node, thus GASPI does not enforce a symmetric memory model unlike for example OpenSHMEM [5]. In comparison to MPI, GASPI employs explicit synchronization. The only technique to ensure that a remote memory access has been completed is by exchanging explicit notifications.

C. Related Work

For this paper, two areas of related work are of particular interest: work on (1) *benchmark suites* and (2) *reproducibility*. Two main types of benchmarks can be distinguished [6]: microbenchmarks and application benchmarks. Especially with respect to parallel programming models, there are plenty of microbenchmarks already available. The *OSU Micro-Benchmarks* (OMB) [7] suite is well-known and widely used to assess the performance of MPI operations. It also includes PGAS microbenchmarks for OpenSHMEM, UPC and UPC++. Another PGAS example is the *UPC Operations Microbenchmarking Suite* (UOMS) [8]. As indicated by its name, the *OpenSHMEM Benchmark Suite* (OBS) [5] includes microbenchmarks, application kernels, and applications for OpenSHMEM. OBS contains MPI and OpenSHMEM variants of the included application benchmarks. Another example is *MerBench* [9], which is a set of UPC benchmarks that capture the communication patterns of the parallel algorithms throughout HipMer, a parallel genome assembler pipeline that has been shown to scale to massive concurrencies. Pophale et al. [10] port the NAS parallel benchmarks with OpenSHMEM and perform a case study on three different platforms. Nonetheless, to the best of the author’s knowledge, the implementations and outputs of the listed benchmarks all differ and do not follow a standardized approach, which makes it difficult to compare the performance of different PGAS programming languages and language extensions and MPI.

The foundation of scientific and engineering research rests upon the expectations of rigor and transparency among those involved in conducting such research. Within the HPC community, there are reproducibility initiatives [11], most notably the SC Conference Series, aimed at improving rigor and transparency. Our approach follows previous work on principles of reproducibility [11]–[13] and presentation of

performance results [14]. Papadopoulos et al. [12] describe eight methodological principles for reproducible performance evaluation, which includes repeated experiments, workload and configuration coverage, experimental setup description, open access artifacts, and statistical evaluation. Hoefler et al. [14] complement this work by describing twelve rules on how to report benchmarking results. We employ these principles and strategies in our design to facilitate reproducibility.

III. MOTIVATION: REPRODUCIBLE BENCHMARKING

Reproducibility is crucial for benchmarking HPC systems for several reasons. First, reproducing the results of benchmarks allows researchers and developers to *validate and verify the correctness* of the benchmarking methodology and implementation. It ensures that the results are not due to errors or inconsistencies in the benchmark code, compiler optimizations, or hardware variations. Furthermore, reproducibility enables *fair and accurate comparisons* between different systems, architectures, or software implementations. Without reproducible results, it is challenging to assess the performance characteristics and make meaningful comparisons. Microbenchmarks measure small, low-level operations. These components can be sensitive to changes in hardware, software, or environmental conditions. Reproducing results helps detect and quantify the impact of such variations on *benchmark stability*. Finally, benchmarks often serve as a *reference point for assessing performance* improvements or regressions over time. Reproducibility allows historical comparisons, which are valuable for tracking performance trends and making informed decisions.

A. Case Study: GPI-2 Microbenchmarks

GPI-2 [15], implemented by Fraunhofer ITWM, is currently the only implementation of the GASPI standard. Since GASPI is a relatively new PGAS API, the amount of available benchmarks is limited. Currently, only GPI-2 provides a set of microbenchmarks. In addition, application benchmarks are not available. To analyze the requirements for a reproducible microbenchmark suite, we investigate the GPI-2 microbenchmarks. To enable reproducible benchmarking, criteria such as *configurability*, *completeness* and *compliance with the standard under consideration* must be taken into account.

Configurable benchmarks enable realistic simulation, fair comparisons, and optimization testing by allowing users to tailor benchmark parameters to match specific workloads, environments, and use cases, therefore enhancing relevance and usefulness. Unlike well-known suites such as the OMB, the configuration of the GPI-2 microbenchmarks cannot be changed without modifying and recompiling the source code. For example, if parameters such as iterations, warm-up iterations and window size are to be adjusted, the counting variables of the measuring loops must be modified for this and the calculation of the results must be adjusted.

The completeness of microbenchmarks is vital because it ensures that all relevant aspects of a programming standard,

including all operations, are thoroughly tested. The comprehensive evaluation helps uncover potential performance bottlenecks or optimizations, providing a more accurate and actionable assessment for system tuning and improvement. The GPI-2 microbenchmarks are incomplete and do not cover all operations described in the GASPI standard.

Compliance with the programming standard is essential for microbenchmarks because it ensures that benchmarking code adheres to the defined rules and practices of the standard. This consistency allows for fair, accurate, and meaningful comparisons between different implementations, helping to validate and verify the standard’s performance expectations and assess its real-world applicability. The GPI-2 benchmark code does not check the return values of the used GASPI operations, therefore violating the GASPI standard. The check of the return values is especially important for extended one-sided communication, because here, depending on the network technology used, the queues can overflow and data can be lost.

The impact on the performance and accuracy of the GPI-2 microbenchmarks results is discussed in Section V-D.

IV. GBS: GASPI BENCHMARK SUITE

In the absence of real GASPI application code, microbenchmarks and application kernels are the only assessments available to compare and analyze the different features and available implementations. The *GASPI Benchmark Suite* (GBS) is one such collection to evaluate the GASPI standard and the GPI-2 [1] library, its implementation. Given the shortcomings of GPI-2 microbenchmarks, we aim to design a benchmark suite that enables reproducible benchmarking while addressing configurability, completeness, and standards compliance.

A. Microbenchmarks

Analysis of existing microbenchmark codes, such as the OMB or the GPI-2 microbenchmark, shows a similar approach to the design and implementation of the benchmark measurement loop structure. Algorithm 1 illustrates the extracted loop structure, which consists of up to three nested loops. Here, the outermost loop provides the parameter that is used as a variable for the benchmark series. We refer to it as the *parameter loop*. In this case, it is used for the message size, i.e. the number of bytes transmitted over the network. This is followed by the *iteration loop*, which repeats the actual measurement several times to produce a meaningful statistical value. The innermost loops are called *window size loop*. In bandwidth measurements, it is used to perform multiple data transfers using successive portions of the buffer provided. Latency benchmarks may omit this inner loop.

The GBS microbenchmarks are designed to perform a minimal test for each GASPI communication primitive. A total of 19 benchmarks have been implemented. The benchmarks are divided into seven different *benchmark groups*, which are refined by three *benchmark subtypes*, as listed in Table I. The table also shows the configurable benchmark parameters. Parameters like *window size*, *min message size* and *max message size* are used to control the behavior of the

Data: Message Size $m > 0$, Iterations $i > 0$, Window Size $w > 0$

```

M ← 1;
while M ≠ m do
  I ← 0;
  B ← allocate(M);
  while I < i do
    T ← Time();
    W ← 0;
    while W < w do
      C ← B + W · M;
      communicate(C, M);
      W ← W + 1;
    end
    T ← Time() − T;
    I ← I + 1;
  end
  deallocate(B);
  M ← M · 2;
end

```

Algorithm 1: Typical benchmark loop structure.

parameter and window size loop. With *single buffer* the memory *allocation* and *deallocation* for the used buffer and also the memory access pattern can be changed. The benchmark results can be obtained in a table format or directly in CSV (Comma Separated Value) format. The output always consists of minimum, maximum, mean, median, standard deviation and the variance. It is supplemented by benchmark-specific information, e.g. buffer elements for reduction operations. All listed benchmarks, except `gbs_info`, also accept parameters for the number of iterations and warm-up iterations. Next, we introduce the seven benchmark groups:

a) *One-Sided*: The *One-Sided Benchmark* group consists of various codes for bandwidth and latency measurements for `gaspi_{write,read}` communication primitives. Figure 2a depicts the communication scheme for the write benchmark. The set of write benchmarks is completed by the `gbs_write_bibw` benchmark, which provides bidirectional bandwidth by implementing simultaneous writes between two different processes, as shown in Figure 2b.

b) *One-Sided-Extended*: The *One-Sided-Extended* group also contains benchmarks encoded for bandwidth and latency measurements. GASPI provides read and write operations combined with notification, as shown in Figure 2c. By extending the usual one-sided communication primitives, the target process is enabled to actively check (`gaspi_notify_wait`) for changes and accesses to its exposed memory segments.

c) *Collective*: The *Collective* group provides codes to evaluate the latency of the GASPI collective operations `gaspi_allreduce` and `gaspi_barrier`.

d) *Atomic*: GASPI offers atomic primitives to perform either *fetch and add* (`fadd`) or *compare and swap* (`cas`)

TABLE I: Benchmark suite overview.

Benchmark	Benchmark Group	Sub Type	window size	min message size	max message size	single buffer
gbs_read_bw	One-Sided	Bandwidth	✓	✓	✓	✓
gbs_write_bw	One-Sided	Bandwidth	✓	✓	✓	✓
gbs_write_bibw	One-Sided	Bandwidth	✓	✓	✓	✓
gbs_write_lat	One-Sided	Latency	✗	✓	✓	✓
gbs_read_lat	One-Sided	Latency	✗	✓	✓	✓
gbs_read_notify_bw	One-Sided-Extended	Bandwidth	✓	✓	✓	✓
gbs_write_notify_bw	One-Sided-Extended	Bandwidth	✓	✓	✓	✓
gbs_write_notify_bibw	One-Sided-Extended	Bandwidth	✓	✓	✓	✓
gbs_write_notify_lat	One-Sided-Extended	Bandwidth	✗	✓	✓	✓
gbs_read_notify_lat	One-Sided-Extended	Latency	✗	✓	✓	✓
gbs_allreduce	Collective	Latency	✗	✓	✓	✓
gbs_barrier	Collective	Latency	✗	✗	✗	✗
gbs_atomic_cas	Atomic	Latency	✗	✗	✗	✗
gbs_atomic_fadd	Atomic	Latency	✗	✗	✗	✗
gbs_passive_bw	Passive	Bandwidth	✓	✓	✓	✓
gbs_passive_lat	Passive	Latency	✗	✓	✓	✓
gbs_notification_ping_pong	Notification	Latency	✗	✓	✓	✓
gbs_notification_rate	Notification	Notification Rate	✗	✓	✓	✓
gbs_info	Information	-	✗	✗	✗	✗

Fig. 2: Overview of different GASPI write benchmark cases.

operations on a remote variable. The *Atomic* group provides latency benchmarks.

e) *Passive*: Passive communication schemes in GASPI can be used similarly to the *send-receive* scheme in MPI. The bandwidth benchmark performs a sequence of sends that are received by the target process. After successfully receiving the expected amount of data, the target process sends a message back to the source process indicating the completion of the operation. For the latency benchmark, a ping-pong scheme has been implemented, i.e. a single message is sent to the target process and waiting for its response.

f) *Notification*: The *Notification* group is based on the GASPI notification primitives. A notification is a write request of a single integer value. As with the passive communication latency benchmark, the ping-pong communication scheme is used to capture latency. The group is completed by a benchmark that measures the transmission of a fixed number of notifications to determine the total number of notifications that can be sent in a single second.

g) *Information*: This group extracts GASPI-specific information, such as the number of available memory segments or the number of requests that fit into a single GASPI queue.

B. Application Kernels

GBS is complemented by three application kernels, which adopt common communication patterns found in HPC appli-

cations. Their purpose is to show the way of integrating new programming paradigms into real computational challenges and to evaluate the performance of programming models like GASPI for actual use cases.

a) *Himeno Benchmark*: The Himeno benchmark, named after its developer Ryutaro Himeno, uses the Jacobi iteration method to solve a system of Poisson equations. It was originally part of a Navier-Stokes solver used for the analysis of incompressible fluids. The implementation of the Jacobi method yields a stencil code. A stencil is a special access pattern in which individual values in a group of points are updated depending on the values of their neighboring grid points. The method can be easily parallelized and vectorized due its regular access pattern.

For parallel execution, the grid is divided into smaller parts distributed across the process domain so that each process computes a small part of the global solution. Since neighboring values are needed to compute updates for other grid points, neighboring processes must exchange all values on the boundaries of their local grid with their neighbors after each iteration. This technique is referred to as ghost cell communication, also known as halo exchange pattern. The Himeno benchmark is not used to compute real solutions to physical problems, but to measure the maximum floating point performance of a given system [16].

b) *SSCAI Benchmark*: The *SSCAI* benchmark [17] implements a Smith-Waterman local sequence alignment algorithm with Godah’s improvements for gap scoring. The benchmark used here is an adaptation of a benchmark already optimized for OpenSHMEM [5]. Its value in benchmarking GASPI libraries is that it can be used to test strategies in managing many small messages with PUT and GET operations issued in the same inner loop. The benchmark is also implemented in a multithreaded version with OpenMP.

c) *RandomAccess Benchmark*: The Random Access Benchmark was originally developed by David Koester and Bob Lucas and is now part of the HPC Challenge Benchmark [18]. Our adaptation is based on the version published by Oak Ridge National Laboratory [5], which includes a version for OpenSHMEM and MPI. This allows for a direct comparison between GASPI, OpenSHMEM, and MPI performance results. The Giga Updates per Second (GUPS) are calculated by identifying the number of memory locations that can be randomly updated in one second, divided by 1 billion. The term “randomly” in this context means that there is little to no relationship between one address to be updated and the next. An update is a read-modify-write operation on a table of 64-bit words. The application kernels are also implemented in a multithreaded version with OpenMP.

V. EVALUATION

We divide the evaluation of our microbenchmark suite into two parts. First, we compare the achievable performance with the one-sided communication introduced by MPI using the *OSU Micro Benchmarks* (OMB) [7]. Then, we use the in GPI-2 microbenchmarks to evaluate the performance and correctness of our implementation. In doing so, we also examine the differences between the two implementations and their impact on the performance results.

During the experiments, the cluster was used exclusively for our measurements. Therefore, the results are not affected by noise within the network caused by other jobs and users. We used the same setup for all presented performance results, i.e. each graph shows the arithmetic mean of ten independent benchmark runs covering different machines of the used cluster to account for possible performance differences.

A. Test Environment

We perform our tests on the *Cesari-MSQC Cluster* at Goethe University Frankfurt. *Cesari-MSQC* is a small general-purpose cluster based on Intel CPU architectures running Rocky Linux 8.7 (Green Obsidian) with Kernel Version 4.18.0 and Slurm. The system consists of 16 nodes each powered by 2x Intel Xeon E5-2660 v2 (Ivy Bridge) in a dual socket configuration, with 32 GB of RAM and FDR InfiniBand.

B. Primer on MPI and GASPI Memory Models

In this section, we give a brief introduction to the memory model of one-sided MPI communication primitives and show how it differs from the GASPI model. The MPI standard distinguishes between two different memory models, *separate*

and *unified*. *Separate* means that there exists two copies of the exposed memory window, one private and one public. *Remote Memory Accesses* (RMA) operations, such as `Put` or `Get` operations, take place on the public copy, while `load` and `store` operations modify the private copy. Public and private window copies must be explicitly synchronized by calling `MPI_Win_sync`. In contrast, there are no private and public copies in the unified memory model. Finally, updates to RMA operations are observed by `load` operations without additional library calls, and the same is true for the visibility of `store` operations to RMA calls.

In general RMA operations can be classified as either *active target communication* (ATC) or *passive target communication* (PTC). ATC takes place in data movements between two processes in which both are involved, i.e. one process transfers the data, the second process is only involved in the subsequent synchronization. PTC defines the process of moving data from one process memory to another, involving only the source process. This paradigm can be used to introduce the notion of *shared memory*, i.e., two source processes communicate with each other by modifying a memory location in the memory of another process that is not explicitly involved in the communication. MPI’s RMA communication calls usually operate on window objects and include the restriction that they can only be executed during an *access epoch* for the target window. Access epochs can be started and stopped using one of the provided synchronization calls on the target window. Active target communication requires the presence of an *exposure epoch* that can be started and stopped by synchronization calls to the target process.

For ATC, the synchronization calls are `MPI_Win_fence`, suitable for loosely synchronous algorithms and `MPI_Win_{start,complete,post,wait}`. The latter form the *Post Send Complete Wait* (PSCW) synchronization sequence, which can be efficiently used for mostly static communication patterns where communication takes place between a small number of logical neighbors. For PTC, the offers are `MPI_Win_lock` and `MPI_Win_lock_all` with their corresponding unlock routines. In addition to PTC synchronization calls, the `MPI_Win_flush` and `MPI_Win_flush_local` exist. These calls can be used to ensure completion of RMA calls for both the source and the target, but for the latter only locally [19].

The GASPI standard introduces the concept of *Memory Segments* which can be seen as the equivalent to the MPI Memory Windows. Unlike MPI, these segments are not based on a specific memory model to provide maximum flexibility. In addition, GASPI does not define strong memory synchronization primitives and patterns, but provides *Notifications* that can be used to inform the target process that an RMA call has just occurred [2]. Since both the MPI and GASPI approach to one-sided communication are very different, the performance comparison is affected by the use of synchronization primitives. Figure 3 shows the achieved bandwidth for both `MPI_Get` and `MPI_Get` using different synchronization

Fig. 3: One-sided communication bandwidth results for OpenMPI with different synchronization techniques.

Fig. 4: One-sided communication bandwidth results for GPI-2 and OpenMPI.

and communication models for message sizes from 2^0 to 2^{22} bytes. The performance data was obtained using the default OMB configuration. It can be observed that the `flush` and `flush_local` primitives provide the best bandwidth. This result was expected since flush operations can only be used during access epochs. Thus the OMB starts an access epoch before the actual measurement by calling `MPI_Win_lock`. Among the synchronization primitives, PSCW yields the worst performance. Another observation is that once the saturation point of the network is reached, the impact of the synchronization used on the performance is negligible. GASPI offers the `gaspi_wait` primitive which incorporates equivalent behavior as the `MPI_Win_flush_local` call. Therefore, further presented MPI performance results will make use of distinct primitive.

C. Comparing GASPI and MPI Performance Results

Traditionally, MPI has been the library of choice for HPC applications. Therefore, GPI-2 and all other PGAS communication libraries must compete with its performance and ease of use. In this experimental setup, we use GBS to collect conclusive performance results and evaluate the effectiveness and capabilities of GPI-2. Due to the brevity of this work, only results for classical *read* and *write* RMA semantics and *collective* operations are presented. In contrast to the extensive set of MPI collectives, the GASPI standard only defines the collective operations *barrier* and *allreduce* [20].

We used the standard OMB configuration for the read and write benchmarks. This means that each data point is measured 1000 times with an additional 100 warm-up iterations. The OMB benchmark paradigm ensures that not only one operation is performed to get a bandwidth result. There is a separate parameter that controls the number of read and write operations for the same message size called *window size*. Also, each operation is executed using its own memory chunk. Effectively, the parameter is used to move a memory window over a buffer of length $\text{buffer length} = \text{message size} \cdot \text{window size}$. Figure 4 shows the results of the bandwidth measurements for message sizes from 2^0 to 2^{22} bytes are shown. For the read operation, it can be observed that GPI-2 is able to achieve higher bandwidth for message sizes between 2^5 and 2^{12} bytes. Both libraries suffer from a performance degradation for message sizes larger than 2^{17} bytes. In contrast, the results of the write RMA experiments show very similar performance for both GPI-2 and MPI. Only GPI-2 suffers a performance loss, again for message sizes larger than 2^{17} bytes. In addition to the MPI results, we need to recall the information from Section V-B. The local flush operation is only usable during an access epoch, which means that in a real world application it is encapsulated e.g. a lock protected epoch, which would notably affect the performance.

For the allreduce experiment, we used buffer sizes from 1 up to 128 elements in powers of two to calculate the element-wise sum. The GASPI standard defines an upper limit for elements that can be used for the allreduce operation. This

Fig. 5: Allreduce latency results for GPI-2 and OpenMPI.

limit can be checked with *gbs_info* and is 255 elements in our case. Since the performance of collective operations naturally deteriorates as the number of participating processes increases, we collected results for two, four, and eight compute nodes. The benchmark runs were performed for the same number of processes per node (PPN) for each of the three node configurations, i.e., one, two, four, and eight with an iteration count of 1000 and 10 warm-up iterations. Figure 5 depicts the achieved latency results for the collective allreduce operation. Looking at the *gaspi_allreduce* shows that doubling the PPN or the number of nodes results in nearly twice the latency. In contrast, the scaling behavior of the MPI allreduce implementations is significantly better in almost all cases. One exception is an artifact consisting of two consecutive data points that have very poor latency values. These outliers occur with different buffer element counts, but appear to be systematic. Further analysis would be required here.

The second collective benchmark measures the latency of the barrier process. We ran the experiments for two, four, and eight nodes with one, two, four, and eight PPN, respectively. All results were obtained with an iteration count of 1000000 and 10 warm-up iterations. Since the results are close to those of the allreduce experiments, we have omitted them here.

D. Comparing GBS and GPI-2 Microbenchmarks

As discussed in Section V-D, GPI-2 comes with its own set of microbenchmarks. Therefore, it is necessary to compare the results of both benchmark suites. In particular, it is of interest how the differences in design and implementation

affect the observed performance. Unlike OMB and GBS, the configuration of the GPI-2 benchmark cannot be adjusted via parameters. In addition, GPI-2 reports its performance numbers as the median of the collected data points. For ease of use and to allow for a better comparison, we have integrated the GPI-2 benchmark code into the GBS suite and changed the output statistic from median to arithmetic mean. For the experiments, we ran both GPI-2 and GBS with the same benchmark settings, i.e., message sizes of 2^1 to 2^{23} , 10 iterations per data point with no warm-up iterations, and a window size of 1000. Due to the brevity of this work, only the bandwidth results for *gaspi_read* and *gaspi_write* are presented as examples.

Figure 6 shows the obtained bandwidth results for both benchmark suites. For read operations, GBS achieves a slightly higher bandwidth than GPI-2. As also observed in previous experiments, GBS bandwidth suffers from some degradation after the saturation point. In contrast, both curves show similar results for the write operation. In this case, GBS also achieves a slightly better bandwidth near the saturation point. In general, the curve representing the GPI-2 results seems to be more stable.

During the experiments we discovered problems within the GPI-2 code. The code does not check the return value of the GASPI calls used. In most cases, this does not affect benchmark execution, but it does for GASPI's extended one-sided communication calls. These calls add an additional notification to the read or write operations, which takes up additional space in the GASPI queue used. For our cluster,

Fig. 6: Remote write throughput for the GPI-2 benchmark and the GBS benchmark suite.

Fig. 7: Write throughput results for different buffer modes and timing methods.

Fig. 8: Read throughput results for different buffer modes and timing methods.

gbs_info shows a request limit of 1024 for a single queue. Using the window size of 1000 for extended one-sided communication calls can result in a state where the queue is full because processing requests typically takes more time than adding new communication requests to the queue. A full queue results in a GASPI error code indicating the state of the queue. This scenario is not included in the GPI-2 code. GBS, on the other hand, provides return value checks for GASPI calls that terminate the program in case of an error. The extended one-sided communication benchmark codes end with an erroneous queue state for window size iterations of > 512 on our test system. In contrast, the GPI-2 code shows the deceptive prospect of correct program execution even though it is limited by the same queue depth, resulting in incorrect performance numbers since only a fraction of the

actual work is done. Adding an error check to the GPI-2 code results in a program termination at the same boundary as GBS.

After comparing results of GPI-2 and GBS, we further investigated the differences between both codes. In doing so, we found that unlike GBS, the GPI-2 code does not use standard timing mechanisms such as `clock_gettime`. The timing method used `gaspi_time_ticks`, which multiplied by the reciprocal of the CPU frequency results in a time. Furthermore, the GPI-2 code uses a single memory allocation throughout the benchmark run, covering the entire message size range. This aspect is fundamentally different from the memory usage in GBS and for example OMB. Therefore, we modified the GBS code so that it can change the memory usage mode between the so-called *single buffer mode*, as in the GPI-2 implementation, and the *multiple buffer mode*,

where for each new message size a new buffer with a length of message size \cdot window size is allocated. By modifying the GBS timing function to dynamically change between `clock_gettime` and `gaspi_time_ticks`, we can also evaluate the impact of timing on observed results.

For the next experiment, we used the GBS code with the GPI-2 benchmark configuration. Again, only the results for reads and writes are given. Figure 7 shows the bandwidth results for the write operations for both available timing modes and also for the two different memory allocation modes. Analysis of the data leads to the conclusion that the choice of the two timing functions has a minimal effect on the overall result. The choice of memory allocation mode, on the other hand, has a significant impact on the observed bandwidth. It can be seen that the saturation point of the multiple buffer curve is lower than that of the single buffer mode. We suspect a correlation with the handling of memory pages, because above a message size of 2^{12} , a doubling of the message size also means a doubling of the number of memory pages used. Effectively, we can describe the multiple buffer approach as *cold memory*, while the single buffer approach can be described as *hot memory*. The same results can be observed for the read operation shown in Figure 8. By using the single buffer mode, we can compensate for the characteristic shape of the read curve.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we have addressed design criteria for reproducible benchmarking using the parallel programming model GASPI. First, we analyzed existing microbenchmarks such as GPI-2 and OMB. From these findings, we derived the GBS benchmark suite, which provides exhaustive microbenchmarks and application kernels for common communication patterns for GASPI. We then demonstrated the effectiveness of GBS by evaluating its performance on our a small testbed. To test its robustness and accuracy, we compared the performance results with MPI and GPI-2. In future work, we want to extend this work to include additional PGAS implementations such as OpenSHMEM, UPC++ and Charm++. We also want to further analyze the impact of different memory models on the overall performance results. The source code of GBS and further information is available on our GitHub companion page: <https://github.com/msqc-goethe/gaspi-benchmark-suite>.

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